

SPG Mitteilungen Communications de la SSP

Auszug - Extrait

The Nobel Prize in Physics 2023: The birth of attosecond science

Lukas Gallmann, ETH Zürich

This article has been downloaded from:
https://www.sps.ch/articles/nobel_prizes/

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10676670](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10676670)

The Nobel Prize in Physics 2023: The birth of attosecond science

Lukas Gallmann, ETH Zürich

1. Introduction

The 2023 Nobel Prize in Physics was awarded to **Anne l’Huillier**, **Pierre Agostini** and **Ferenc Krausz** “for experimental methods that generate attosecond pulses of light for the study of electron dynamics in matter”. With their contributions, the three laureates pioneered the field of attosecond science. In this article, I will describe the history behind the development of this field, the underlying physics and the technology that made all of this possible. Some background on the generation of attosecond pulses, the experimental techniques in attosecond time-resolved spectroscopy and their application for studying ultrafast dynamics in solids can be found in an earlier article in the *SPG Mitteilungen* Nr. 57 [1].

2. Of atoms and photons

Attosecond science has one of its roots in a sub-domain of atomic physics that studied the interaction of intense laser pulses with atoms. In the late 1970s and throughout the 1980s an intense field of study (also in the literal sense) was the ionization of atoms through the simultaneous absorption of multiple photons. The investigation of such processes was made possible by laser amplifiers now reaching focused peak intensities on the order of 10^{13} - 10^{14} W/cm². Researchers observed that under irradiation with intense laser pulses, atoms can absorb tens of photons simultaneously and highly charged ion species can be produced with photons that individually possess only a fraction of the energy needed to overcome the ionization threshold of the neutral atom.

The laser technology of that time mainly relied on Nd³⁺ doped materials, emitting radiation around 1064 nm. Instead of the fundamental, many multi-photon ionization studies used frequency-doubled, -tripled, or even -quadrupled light. This is because the nonlinear optical frequency-conversion improves pulse contrast and focusability of the beam while at the same time fewer photons are needed to bridge the ionization threshold.

However, such powerful lasers were too large and expensive for regular university-scale laboratories and available only at specialized research facilities. Both, Pierre Agostini and Anne l’Huillier spent their early careers at the same leading center for intense laser science in Gif-sur-Yvette near Paris. An example of Pierre Agostini’s work from that time is his report of the first observation of electrons absorbing one photon more than they needed to overcome the ionization threshold of xenon [2]. Later it was found that in the underlying process of above-threshold ionization large numbers of excess photons can be absorbed simultaneously. An example of Anne l’Huillier’s early work, on the other hand, is an experiment where she showed how the absorption of additional photons above the single-ionization threshold can lead to the formation of multiply charged krypton ions [3].

An important step towards the development of attosecond science happened, when researchers shifted their attention from the ions and electrons to the electro-magnetic radiation being generated in these interactions. In 1987, McPherson and co-workers reported the production of vacuum-ultraviolet light at odd-order harmonics of the 248-nm driving laser wavelength [4]. The highest observed harmonic was the 17th, corresponding to a wavelength of 14.6 nm. Probably the most important result of that paper was that the authors found a significant change in the intensity-scaling of the associated conversion efficiencies around harmonics 9 and 11. This was an early indication that the mechanisms responsible for the generation of low and high harmonic orders are not the same.

Only a year later, Anne l’Huillier and co-workers observed all the hallmark features of the process soon-to-be-known as high-harmonic generation (HHG) [5]. This work reported the first clear evidence of the so-called plateau and cut-off of the HHG spectrum. This was possible because the team used a longer driving laser wavelength of 1064 nm compared to earlier studies, which is also more representative of how HHG is performed today. Why this is the case, is explained below.

Figure 1 displays the typical structure of a HHG spectrum. Conversion efficiencies into the lowest harmonics drop exponentially with harmonic order. Above a certain harmonic

Figure 1: a) Typical structure of a high-harmonic spectrum. At a given laser intensity, the strength of the lowest harmonics drops exponentially with harmonic order. Above harmonics 9 to 11, however, their strength only weakly changes – a clear sign for a non-perturbative interaction. On the high-energy side again a rapid drop of the harmonic signal is observed. This is called the cut-off region. b) Semi-classical three-step model of high-harmonic generation. The strong electric field of the laser distorts the Coulomb potential of an atom and creates a tunnel barrier for the most weakly bound electron. The liberated electron is then accelerated in the oscillating light field and may eventually return to the parent ion. The returning electron can recombine with the ion and emits excess energy as a high-energy photon. The periodic oscillation of the light field results in a periodic repetition of these steps, which results in the formation of discrete odd harmonics in spectral domain.

order, conversion efficiencies remain almost constant over a large number of harmonics. This region is known as the plateau. At the highest observed harmonics, another rapid drop in efficiency occurs. This region of harmonic orders or photon energies is known as the cut-off.

In traditional nonlinear optics, harmonic generation is understood as a perturbative process. The different orders of nonlinear processes are obtained through a Taylor expansion of the time-dependent polarization with respect to the driving electric field. Such a perturbative approach is only justified if the importance of the different terms of the Taylor expansion drops rapidly with their order. The appearance of a plateau in the HHG spectrum is a clear sign for the breakdown of perturbative nonlinear optics.

The early 1990s brought rapid progress in the theoretical understanding of the phenomena observed by experimentalists in prior years. It was found that HHG can be described successfully as a single-electron effect [6] and that it is based on re-scattering of this laser-driven electron wavepacket with its parent ion [7, 8]. The cut-off energy was found – aside from a constant offset given by the ionization energy of the irradiated atom – to be proportional to the driving laser intensity and its wavelength squared [9]. This wavelength scaling explains why clear evidence for the existence of a plateau and cut-off was found in the work by l’Huillier and co-workers using a 1064-nm laser [5], but not in the earlier papers on harmonic generation using shorter-wavelength drivers. A full quantum-mechanical model introduced by Maciej Lewenstein in 1994 confirmed the main findings of the earlier semi-classical models [10].

A particularly popular model for describing the HHG process is the semi-classical three-step model [8], which intuitively explains many of the important properties of this effect. It describes HHG as a tunnel-ionization event resulting from the distortion of the atomic potential due to the strong laser field, followed by a Newtonian acceleration of the liberated electron in that field. If the ionization step is timed correctly with regards to the accelerating field, the electron can return to its parent ion and recombine. Upon recombination it releases excess energy in the form of an energetic photon. As the process periodically repeats with each half oscillation cycle of the driving laser field, these photons are emitted as odd-order harmonics of the original laser frequency.

In parallel to the development of theoretical frameworks describing HHG, first proposals for using HHG for the generation of attosecond pulses appeared [11, 12]. These ideas were motivated by the extremely large optical bandwidths covered by the plateau harmonics, which could be used to synthesize short field transients in time domain. However, it took another decade until these proposals were made a reality [13].

3. A technology-enabled route

The invention of chirped-pulse amplification by Strickland and Mourou in 1985 [14], which was awarded with the 2018 Nobel Prize in Physics, was a game-changer (see also *SPG Mitteilungen* Nr. 57, p. 40). On one hand, it allowed to increase the peak intensities that can be reached by laser amplifiers by many orders of magnitude. More important for

the field of attosecond science, it made the laser intensities that are needed for HHG and related phenomena accessible with compact and relatively inexpensive table-top laser systems.

Around the same time, Ti:sapphire was discovered as a new laser gain material [15, 16]. Due to its extremely large amplification bandwidth (still the broadest to date), Ti:sapphire supports pulses with durations down to a few femtoseconds (10^{-15} s) from laser oscillators or down to about 20 fs from amplified systems [17]. This is orders of magnitude shorter than what the Nd-based systems were able to offer. With shorter pulses, a given peak intensity can be reached with much less energy per pulse. This therefore represented another important step for reducing size and cost of laser systems capable of HHG. Pulses from Ti:sapphire oscillators typically have energies on the order of few nJ and can reach peak powers approaching 1 MW. Compact table-top amplifiers easily produce mJ level pulse energies and tens of GW peak power.

The discovery of Ti:sapphire and a number of important related technologies triggered a ‘rush for the shortest pulse’ in the 1990s [17]. The third 2023 Nobel Laureate in Physics, Ferenc Krausz, was one of the leading contributors to these developments.

In this context, Krausz’ group invested significant efforts into shortening the energetic pulses from amplified systems. While the finite gain bandwidth of the Ti:sapphire gain material makes it difficult to produce pulses shorter than about 20 fs with amplifiers, nonlinear optical pulse compression schemes allowed to shorten them to the few-fs regime [18], otherwise only accessible with low-energy oscillators. Applying such intense few-cycle pulses for HHG lead to the generation of quasi-continuous extreme ultraviolet spectra already in 1997 [19] – an early hint at the possibility of producing isolated attosecond bursts of radiation from a single driving pulse.

With the shortest generated pulses now lasting only a few oscillation cycles of the underlying electro-magnetic field, the phase of these field oscillations with regards to the pulse envelope started to matter (Figure 2). If, for example, the electric field maximum coincides with the maximum of the pulse envelope (a ‘cosine pulse’), higher peak field strengths are reached than if a zero-crossing of the field occurs at the envelope maximum (‘sine pulse’). For field-dependent physical phenomena, such as HHG, the outcome of the process may depend on this phase between the field (carrier) and its envelope.

Control of this so-called carrier-envelope offset phase became possible around 2000 [20-22]. This was not only an enabling step for attosecond science as we’ll see below, but its frequency domain incarnation also laid the foundation for the application of frequency combs in high-precision frequency metrology, which was a key aspect of the 2005 Nobel Prize in Physics that was awarded to Theodor W. Hänsch and John L. Hall.

The ability to control the electric field of intense few-cycle laser pulses was a prerequisite for the successful demonstration of isolated attosecond pulses – the approach pursued

Figure 2: Importance of carrier-envelope offset phase control for isolated attosecond pulse generation. For very short laser pulses, the phase between their envelope (black dash-dotted line) and their electric field (red line) matters in field-driven processes such as high-harmonic generation. A 'cosine pulse' reaches a higher maximum electric field strength than a 'sine pulse'. The former may produce an isolated attosecond pulse (blue) whereas the latter may yield a double pulse under the same conditions (with appropriate spectral filtering), as the highest field strengths are now reached in two half-oscillation cycles. Without external control, the carrier-envelope offset phase would fluctuate randomly from pulse to pulse and along with this the temporal structure of the generated attosecond bursts.

by Krausz. With such short driving pulses, the cut-off region of the high-harmonic spectrum and the temporal structure of the emission sensitively depend on the carrier-envelope offset phase (Figure 2).

4. Attosecond pulses, finally

Shortly after the turn of the millennium, everything finally came together for the first experimental demonstration of attosecond pulses – interestingly almost at the same time for the two different approaches pursued by Agostini and Krausz [13, 23].

While it was expected that HHG can indeed give rise to the formation of attosecond pulses in the time domain, suitable methods for measuring them needed to be devised.

The approach chosen by the team around Pierre Agostini used longer, multi-cycle pulses (~ 40 fs) to drive the HHG process [13]. These relatively long pulses give rise to narrow, well-defined harmonics in the plateau that are insensitive to the carrier-envelope offset phase of the fundamental. Control of this parameter was therefore not required. A superposition of a set of these odd-order harmonics synthesizes a train of evenly spaced attosecond pulses in the time domain, with two attosecond pulses being emitted per field oscillation cycle of the fundamental.

For their temporal characterization, the team sent the attosecond pulse train into a gas target containing argon atoms. Due to the high photon energy of the individual harmonics forming the pulse train, they could easily single-photon ionize the atoms. The spectrum of the photo-emitted electrons now essentially mimics the energetic structure of the harmonics (minus the energy needed to ionize argon). If one now superimposes a fraction of the original fundamental beam with the attosecond pulse train in the argon target, the resulting interaction can lead the photoelectrons to ab-

sorb or emit a fundamental photon in addition to the already absorbed harmonic photon. From this, quantum path interference can occur between photoelectrons created by odd harmonic ($2N-1$) and the absorption of an additional fundamental photon and photoelectrons created by the next higher odd harmonic ($2N+1$) and the emission of a fundamental photon (N being an integer number). Both possible paths originate from the same ground state and end in the same final state: a photoelectron energy in a sideband between the electrons that were created by the two neighboring harmonics alone.

In this scheme called Reconstruction of Attosecond Beating by Interference of Two-photon Transitions (RABBITT, [24]), the quantum path interference encodes the relative phases of neighboring harmonics. Together with the easily measured optical power spectrum of the high-harmonic radiation, this is everything that is needed to reconstruct the temporal structure of an average of the pulses forming the pulse train. Using this method, Paul et al. reported the generation of a train of 250 as pulses in the June 2001 issue of Science [13].

The approach pursued by the team of Ferenc Krausz called for a different characterization technique. They created isolated attosecond pulses from a field-controlled, few-cycle fundamental, building on the fact that the most energetic high-harmonic radiation is generated only by the strongest electric-field half-cycle in such a short pulse. By definition, this radiation forms the cut-off region of the HHG spectrum. Using a spectral band-pass filter, they extracted this spectral component from the rest of the emission.

Similar to the technique used by Agostini, the attosecond pulse was used to single-photon ionize a rare gas target (krypton in the first demonstration) and, again, the attosecond pulse beam was superimposed with a fraction of the fundamental laser beam. Due to the temporal structure of the

attosecond pulse, emission of photoelectrons is confined to an equally short time interval. From the instant of ionization onwards, the electrons will be accelerated by the superimposed fundamental field. Their final kinetic energy thereby becomes modulated by the electric field of the fundamental. By recording electron spectra as a function of the relative time delay between attosecond pulse and fundamental, one traces out this modulation, which essentially represents a cross-correlation between an electron wavepacket that mimics the time structure of the attosecond pulse and the fundamental field (or, more precisely, its vector potential). The duration of the attosecond pulse can now be inferred from the resulting cross-correlation. The first successful measurement of an isolated attosecond pulse of 650 as duration using this so-called ‘attosecond streak camera’ was reported in the last November issue of *Nature* in 2001 [23].

More details on attosecond pulse generation, the related measurement techniques and their applications can be found in [1].

5. Attosecond pulses, what are they good for?

The attentive reader may have spotted that the measurement methods used to characterize the first attosecond pulses – isolated or trains – should also encode information about the photoemission process that forms the foundation of these techniques. Indeed, the very same methods allowed for the first time to study the dynamics of the photoemission process itself.

For example, in 2010, the Krausz group measured a relative delay of 20 as between electrons emitted from 2s and 2p orbitals of neon using ~90 eV photons and the attosecond streak camera technique [25]. Shortly after, the l’Huillier group reported delays of 110 as between 3s and 3p electrons from argon using the RABBITT method with harmonics between 30 and 40 eV photon energy [26]. Such studies of the dynamics of photo-ionization phenomena remained at the focus of attosecond science for many years.

It can be noted that atomic nuclei are generally too heavy to exhibit a significant dynamical response on sub-femtosecond scales. Attosecond science therefore studies the response of the electrons and associated phenomena. How does charge redistribute in a molecule following the removal of an electron? How is energy flowing on atomic scales after absorption of a photon? How do the electrons in a solid respond to a strong laser field? These are just a few example questions that can be addressed in modern attosecond science.

During the first years after the first successful demonstrations of attosecond pulses, only very few groups managed to perform experiments with them and even for the groups that mastered the techniques, intervals between successive publications remained long. This was not due to a lack of interest as almost all first papers were published in high-profile journals, but it reflected how technically challenging these experiments were. In addition, while the theory of HHG and attosecond pulse generation was already mature by the time the experimentalist groups succeeded, the same thing cannot be said about the theories describing the studied attosecond phenomena – not least because of

the time-resolved nature of the experiments.

However, during the last decade the field gained significant momentum and has expanded to a wide range of physical systems of increasing complexity. These systems now include molecules of sizes up to amino acids in gas phase or solution, liquids and a wide range of solid-state materials. As the experimentalists push the frontiers, theorists are quickly catching up with their models and descriptions of these systems on the involved scales.

As a detailed discussion of the capabilities of attosecond science and recent developments in the field goes well beyond the scope of this article, the reader is referred to some of the many excellent review articles on the topic (e.g., [27-30]).

6. Conclusion and outlook

At first sight it may have been surprising that the Nobel Committee awarded the 2023 edition of its physics prize to three experimentalists. Looking at the historical development and the technical challenges that needed to be overcome to turn the vision and early prediction of attosecond-scale time-resolved spectroscopy into a reality, this becomes understandable. Furthermore, the instant at which attosecond pulses became available, experimentalists produced a wide range of observations, which challenged the understanding of physics and the methods used by theorists. Overall, attosecond science is a beautiful example of the fruitful interplay of theory and experiment in physics.

Based on paradigms of traditional ultrafast time-resolved spectroscopy, the initial suspicion was that isolated attosecond pulses would prove to be more useful than the attosecond pulse train approach. However, from today’s perspective, more than 20 years after the first experimental demonstrations of the respective techniques, we know that pulse trains are equally powerful for attosecond spectroscopy. In short, since pulse trains are perfectly phase-locked to their generating fundamental wave, in many experiments that use the very same fundamental to drive a process and the pulse train to probe it, each individual pulse in the train probes essentially the same dynamics, yielding in sum the same information a single pulse would (but often with better statistics). The fact that both approaches are equally useful in practice was honored by the Nobel Committee by awarding the prize to Krausz and Agostini, who essentially represent these two incarnations of attosecond pulses.

Anne l’Huillier, on the other hand, is a pioneer of the entire field going back to its early days in intense laser – atom interactions. She not only significantly contributed to the discovery and understanding of high-harmonic generation, which forms the foundation of attosecond science, but since those early days continued to consistently make important contributions to the field. Her group, for example, was responsible for a range of essential contributions to our understanding of the attosecond dynamics of single-photon ionization processes.

The above discussion provides a glimpse of how the field spread from studies of simple atoms into other domains of physics, today including investigations on condensed-phase

systems. On the other hand, with its extension towards increasingly complex molecules in gas phase or even in solution, the field also became relevant for chemists and even biologists. While most of the chemistry and biology happens on comparably slow time scales, these often complex chains of inter-linked processes may start with a very fast one: e.g., the absorption of a photon in a photoreceptor in our eye, followed by a fast redistribution of charge and energy on atomic scales.

At the same time, the exclusivity of HHG as a source of attosecond pulses comes to an end, with more and more XUV or x-ray free-electron lasers (such as SwissFEL at PSI) becoming capable of producing such short flashes of light. Free-electron lasers (FELs) can produce orders-of-magnitude more photons per pulse and generate light at considerably higher photon energies than what HHG will ever be able to. However, FELs will not render the more traditional table-top, lab-based HHG sources obsolete, but rather expand the parameter space for experimental attosecond science in a complementary way. Cost and size of HHG sources, and the coherence and level of control over the generated light fields are difficult to beat. On the other hand, pulse and photon energies from FELs are out of reach for HHG setups. In particular, these high light intensities attainable with FELs open a new route for studying nonlinear optical phenomena with attosecond resolution, further expanding the tool set of attosecond science.

With the scientific scope and technological capabilities of attosecond science still growing, also the number of research groups in this field keeps increasing at a fast pace. Many new insights into fundamental processes and breakthrough results can be expected for years to come. The Nobel Prize in Physics 2023 is therefore not expected to mark the culmination of a research area, but rather celebrates its pioneers, acknowledges that attosecond science has shown its potential and implies that this field is expected to have a lasting impact also for our future.

References

- [1] L. Gallmann, and U. Keller, "Progress in Physics (66): The attosecond science of solids," *SPG Mitteilungen* **57**, 11-17 (2019).
- [2] P. Agostini, F. Fabre, G. Mainfray, G. Petite, and N. K. Rahman, "Free-Free Transitions Following Six-Photon Ionization of Xenon Atoms," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **42**, 1127 (1979).
- [3] A. L'Huillier, L. A. Lompre, G. Mainfray, and C. Manus, "Multiply Charged Ions Formed by Multiphoton Absorption Processes in the Continuum," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **48**, 1814-1817 (1982).
- [4] A. McPherson, G. Gibson, H. Jara, U. Johann, T. S. Luk, I. A. McIntyre, K. Boyer, and C. K. Rhodes, "Studies of multiphoton production of vacuum-ultraviolet radiation in the rare gases," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* **4**, 595-601 (1987).
- [5] M. Ferray, A. L'Huillier, X. F. Li, L. A. Lompre, G. Mainfray, and C. Manus, "Multiple-harmonic conversion of 1064 nm radiation in rare gases," *J. Phys. B: At. Mol. Opt. Phys.* **21**, L31-L35 (1988).
- [6] A. L'Huillier, K. J. Schafer, and K. C. Kulander, "Theoretical aspects of intense field harmonic generation," *J. Phys. B: At. Mol. Opt. Phys.* **24**, 3315-3341 (1991).
- [7] K. C. Kulander, K. J. Schafer, and J. L. Krause, "Dynamics of short-pulse excitation, ionization and harmonic conversion," in *Super-Intense Laser-Atom Physics*, B. Piraux, A. L'Huillier, and K. Rzazewski, eds. (Plenum, New York, 1993), pp. 95-110.
- [8] P. B. Corkum, "Plasma Perspective on Strong-Field Multiphoton Ionization," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **71**, 1994-1997 (1993).
- [9] J. L. Krause, K. J. Schafer, and K. C. Kulander, "High-order harmonic-generation from atoms and ions in the high-intensity regime," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **68**, 3535-3538 (1992).
- [10] M. Lewenstein, P. Balcou, M. Y. Ivanov, A. L'Huillier, and P. B. Corkum, "Theory of high-harmonic generation by low-frequency laser fields," *Phys. Rev. A* **49**, 2117-2132 (1994).
- [11] G. Farkas, and C. Toth, "Proposal for attosecond light pulse generation using laser induced multiple-harmonic conversion processes in rare gases," *Phys. Lett. A* **168**, 447-450 (1992).
- [12] S. E. Harris, J. J. Macklin, and T. W. Hänsch, *Opt. Commun.* **100**, 487 (1993).
- [13] P. M. Paul, E. S. Toma, P. Breger, G. Mullot, F. Augé, P. Balcou, H. G. Muller, and P. Agostini, "Observation of a Train of Attosecond Pulses from High Harmonic Generation," *Science* **292**, 1689-1692 (2001).
- [14] D. Strickland, and G. Mourou, "Compression of amplified chirped optical pulses," *Opt. Commun.* **56**, 219-221 (1985).
- [15] P. F. Moulton, "Ti-doped sapphire: tunable solid-state laser," in *Optics News* (1982), p. 9.
- [16] P. F. Moulton, "Spectroscopic and laser characteristics of $\text{Ti:Al}_2\text{O}_3$," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* **3**, 125-132 (1986).
- [17] G. Steinmeyer, D. H. Sutter, L. Gallmann, N. Matuschek, and U. Keller, "Frontiers in Ultrashort Pulse Generation: Pushing the Limits in Linear and Nonlinear Optics," *Science* **286**, 1507-1512 (1999).
- [18] M. Nisoli, S. De Silvestri, O. Svelto, R. Szipöcs, K. Ferenz, C. Spielmann, S. Sartania, and F. Krausz, "Compression of High Energy Laser Pulses Below 5 fs," *Optics Lett.* **22**, 522-524 (1997).
- [19] C. Spielmann, N. H. Burnett, S. Sartania, R. Koppitsch, M. Schnürer, C. Kan, M. Lenzner, P. Wobrauschek, and F. Krausz, "Generation of Coherent X-rays in the Water Window Using 5-Femtosecond Laser Pulses," *Science* **278**, 661-664 (1997).
- [20] H. R. Telle, G. Steinmeyer, A. E. Dunlop, J. Stenger, D. H. Sutter, and U. Keller, "Carrier-envelope offset phase control: A novel concept for absolute optical frequency measurement and ultrashort pulse generation," *Appl. Phys. B* **69**, 327-332 (1999).
- [21] D. J. Jones, S. A. Diddams, J. K. Ranka, A. Stentz, R. S. Windeler, J. L. Hall, and S. T. Cundiff, "Carrier-envelope phase control of femtosecond mode-locked lasers and direct optical frequency synthesis," *Science* **288**, 635-639 (2000).
- [22] A. Apolonski, A. Poppe, G. Tempea, C. Spielmann, T. Udem, R. Holzwarth, T. W. Hänsch, and F. Krausz, "Controlling the phase evolution of few-cycle light pulses," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **85**, 740-743 (2000).
- [23] M. Hentschel, R. Kienberger, C. Spielmann, G. A. Reider, N. Milosevic, T. Brabec, P. Corkum, U. Heinzmann, M. Drescher, and F. Krausz, "Attosecond metrology," *Nature* **414**, 509-513 (2001).
- [24] H. G. Muller, "Reconstruction of attosecond harmonic beating by interference of two-photon transitions," *Appl. Phys. B* **74**, S17-S21 (2002).
- [25] M. Schultze, M. Fiess, N. Karpowicz, J. Gagnon, M. Korbman, M. Hofstetter, S. Neppl, A. L. Cavalieri, Y. Komninos, T. Mercouris, C. A. Nicolaides, R. Pazourek, S. Nagele, J. Feist, J. Burgdorfer, A. M. Azzeer, R. Ernstorfer, R. Kienberger, U. Kleineberg, E. Goulielmakis, F. Krausz, and V. S. Yakovlev, "Delay in Photoemission," *Science* **328**, 1658-1662 (2010).
- [26] K. Klünder, J. M. Dahlström, M. Gisselbrecht, T. Fordell, M. Swoboda, D. Guenot, P. Johnsson, J. Caillat, J. Mauritsson, A. Maquet, R. Taïeb, and A. L'Huillier, "Probing Single-Photon Ionization on the Attosecond Time Scale," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **106**, 143002 (2011).
- [27] F. Krausz, and M. Y. Ivanov, "Attosecond physics," *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **81**, 163-234 (2009).
- [28] J. Li, J. Lu, A. C. Chew, S. Han, J. Li, Y. Wu, H. Wang, S. Ghimire, and Z. Chang, "Attosecond science based on high harmonic generation from gases and solids," *Nature Commun.* **11**, 2748 (2020).
- [29] F. Calegari, G. Sansone, S. Stagira, C. Vozzi, and M. Nisoli, "Advances in attosecond science," *J. Phys. B: At. Mol. Opt. Phys.* **49**, 062001 (2016).
- [30] L. Gallmann, C. Cirelli, and U. Keller, "Attosecond Science: Recent Highlights and Future Trends," *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.* **63**, 447-469 (2012).